

MANUFACTURING AND CHARACTERIZATION OF THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES USING POLYARYLATE/PET ISLAND-IN-A-SEA FIBERS

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1 Introduction

Application fields of the fiber reinforced composite have been expanded to various engineering parts such as aerospace, civil engineering, electronics, automotive and etc[1-3]. Recently, many researches have been concentrated on the development of fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites due to their many advantages of short processing time, recyclability, solvent-free process, high toughness and impact properties. Thus, in this study, we tried to develop a kind of fiber reinforced thermoplastic composite by using the PAR/PET island-in-a-sea fiber method.

A polyarylate(PAR) is a liquid crystal polymer (LCP) because it has a liquid crystal feature in the molten state, and its chemical structure is shown in Figure 1. When the PAR fiber is prepared by a melt spinning, it offers very high mechanical properties compared with other general fiber due to orientation phenomena during the fiber spinning process as shown in Figure 2. Other advantages of the PAR fiber are great strength-to-weight ratio and dimensional stability. Due to these reasons, the PAR fiber is suitable material for fiber reinforced composites[4-10].

A Polyethylene terephthalate(PET) matrix, thermoplastic resin, is extensively used in industry fields because it has not only high melt flow but also chemical resistance and thermal stability. Its chemical structure is shown in Figure 3. PET resin is a good material as a matrix of composite material, but it is very hard to impregnate the reinforcements with the PET matrix. Impregnation of reinforcing fiber is one of the most difficult problems in manufacturing thermoplastic composites[11-17].

To solve this problem, in this study, the PAR/PET composite was manufactured using the PAR/PET

island-in-a-sea fibers because it is very effective in impregnation process[18]. Especially, when the PAR fiber phase has a nano-fibril structure in the composite, some useful effects are expected such as larger interfacial area and lightweight with high strength to weight ratio [19-23]. In this study, the PAR/PET island-in-a-sea fibers having different spinning conditions such as the spinning speed and the PAR content, were used to manufacture the PAR/PET composite. Characteristics of the PAR/PET island-in-a-sea fiber and its composite were analyzed with various tests and evaluation. Also, property changes of the PAR/PET composites with the processing conditions such as molding temperature and pressure were investigated.

Figure 1. Chemical structure of the PAR

Figure 2. PAR fiber orientation phenomena in spinning process

Figure 3. Chemical structure of the PET

2 Experiments

2.1 Materials and Preparation

The PAR/PET island-in-a-sea fiber was spun by a conjugate spinning technology with spinning temperature of 290°C and die pressure of 58kgf/cm². Also, the number of island-forming nozzle hole was 74. The PAR, a LCP polymer, of the island phase was the Vectra supplied from Kuraray and the PET resin of the sea phase, Huvis SD®, was provided with the Huvis in Korea. Spinning speeds of the island-in-a-sea fiber are 200, 300, and 400m/min and the PAR contents in the fiber are 30, 50 and 70wt%, respectively. All information of the materials used in this study is shown in Table.1.

Before the analysis and manufacturing the composite, all the materials were dried process in vacuum oven at 100°C for 3hours to minimize the effect of moisture.

Table 1. Materials information used in this study

PAR resin	Vectra® (Kuraray)
PET resin	Huvis SD® (Huvis)
PAR content in the island-in-a-sea fiber (wt%)	30, 50, 70 (Spinning speed : 400m/min)
Spinning speed (m/min)	200, 300, 400 (PAR content in the island-in-a-sea fiber : 50wt%)

2.2 Properties of the PAR/PET island-in-a-sea fiber

Tensile test of the PAR/PET island-in-a-sea fiber was performed according to ASTM D 3822 using an

Instron® 4467. The load cell was fixed at 50N and cross-head speed was 2mm/min.

To measure the crystalline structure of the island-in-a-sea fiber spun by different conditions, X-ray diffractometer(XRD) analysis was performed using a D/MAX-2200 Ultima/PC of Rigaku International Co. Also, a wide angle X-ray scattering (WAXD) from Pruker, D8 Discover Int. was used under the 300s of exposure time at room temperature and through this instrument, the 1D-WAXD patterns were obtained. The conditions of the XRD analysis are shown in Table 2. The results of the XRD curves were used to obtain degree of crystallization as spinning speed and the PAR content by integral the area under the crystallization peak.

Also, morphology of cross sectional view of the PAR/PET island-in-a-sea fiber was observed using the scanning electron microscopy(SEM) from JSM-7000F of JEOL Int. The PAR/PET island-in-a-sea fiber was soaked in the liquid nitrogen for 5minutes and then, it was cut using a diamond cutter to obtain clear cross sections.

Table 2. Condition of the XRD analysis

2 theta(°)	0 – 90
Step size	0.02
Exposure time (sec)	300 sec
Generator	40 kV, 45mA
λ (Radiation)	1.5406

2.3 Manufacturing of the PAR/PET composite

Before manufacturing the PAR/PET composite, PAR/PET island-in-a-sea fiber was cleaned using ethyl alcohol for 24 hour at the room temperature to remove contaminant and scouring agent on the fiber surface. After that, it was dried at 30°C for 12 hour in vacuum oven.

The detailed method of manufacturing process is following. Firstly, the PAR/PET island-in-a-sea fibers were arranged uni-directionally on the aluminium plate. And then, prepared plate was put into the hot press and remained for 30 seconds with 5psi of pressure to prepare the unidirectional prepreg without scatter the alignment of the fibers. The

manufactured prepregs were stacked with same direction of the fiber and molded in a hot press with predetermined molding temperature, pressure and time. Figure 4 shows schematics of the PAR/PET composite manufacturing process. During the molding process, the PET phase of the island-in-a-sea fiber melted and became a matrix of the PAR/PET composite. Whereas, the PAR fiber maintained its form, not melted, and became a reinforcement of the composite.

Figure 4. Schematics of the PAR/PET composite manufacturing process

2.4 Molding condition of the PAR/PET composite

Properties of the composite were largely affected by manufacturing conditions such as temperature, pressure and time. The PAR/PET island-in-a-sea fiber (50:50) spun by 400m/min was used for fabricating the composite with various molding conditions.

Using the differential scanning calorimetry(DSC) from Mettler-Toledo DSC1, suitable temperature of composite manufacturing was determined by obtaining the melting point of the PAR and the PET. Heating rate was fixed at 10°C/min with 25 to 300°C of scanning range.

Molding temperature of the PAR/PET composite was varied in the range of 260 to 275°C under the pressure of 500psi for 10min. Also, variations of applied pressure and processing times were 100 to 1000psi and 1 to 10min., respectively.

2.5 Property tests of the PAR/PET composite

Tensile test of the prepared PAR/PET composite was performed according to the ASTM D 3039 using an Instron® model 4467 and cross-head speed was fixed at 2mm/min. Both ends of the samples

were attached sand paper to prevent a slipping and damage of the samples as shown in Figure 5.

Also, Flexural properties of the PAR/PET composite was measured according to the ASTM D 790 using a same machine with the tensile test and its schematics of the sample is shown in Figure 6.

Test method of flexural property was the 3-point bending as shown in Figure 7.

In addition, crystalline properties of the PAR/PET composite were analyzed using a XRD. Changes of crystal form in the PAR fiber were analyzed during the composite manufacturing process by comparing that of the PAR/PET island-in-a-sea fiber. The conditions of the XRD analysis were same as that of the PAR/PET island-in-a-sea fiber. Using a SEM, morphology of the fracture surface of the PAR/PET composite after tensile test was observed.

Figure 5. Schematic of the PAR/PET composite sample in the tensile test

Figure 6. Schematic of the PAR/PET composite sample in the flexural test

Figure 7. Schematic of 3-point bending set-up in the flexural test

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Characteristics of the PAR/PET island-in-a-sea fiber

Tensile properties of the PAR/PET island-in-a-sea fiber

Tensile strength and modulus of the PAR/PET island-in-a-sea fiber as a spinning speed are shown in Figure 8. Tensile strengths of the fibers spun with spinning speed of 200 to 400m/min are slightly different. Overall, as spinning speed increases, tensile properties of the fiber increase a little. Also, tensile modulus of the fiber shows a small difference as well with spinning speed.

On the other hand, tensile properties of the fiber having different the PAR content show a sharp increase as shown in Figure 9. Compared with Figure 8, tensile properties of the PAR/PET island-in-a-sea fiber are more influenced by the PAR content than spinning speed.

Figure 8. Tensile properties of the PAR/PET island-in-a-sea fiber as spinning speed

Figure 9. Tensile properties of the PAR/PET island-in-a-sea fiber as the PAR content

Crystalline structure of the PAR/PET island-in-a-sea fiber

Figure 10 and 11 show the crystallization properties of the PAR/PET island-in-a-sea fiber as spinning speed and the PAR content. Generally, if the peak of XRD curve is sharp and narrow, crystals of the material are formed more obviously. With the results of XRD analysis in this study, the PAR has a very sharp and narrow peak at 20° , while the PET has a broad curve as shown in Figure 10.

Although the PET has low degree of crystallization, the PAR/PET island-in-a-sea fiber has relatively high degree of crystallization. Because the PAR is known as a liquid crystal polymer, when the PAR is included more and more in the fiber, crystalline content in the fiber increases as well. With the decrease of spinning speed, the peaks of the PAR/PET island-in-a-sea fiber are slightly moved to peak of the PET and the height of peak of the fiber is rapidly lower than that of the PAR. Consequently, spinning speed increase, the peak becomes sharp and thus, the crystalline in the PAR/PET island-in-a-sea fiber is formed clearly.

The form of the curves shown in Figure 11 is quite similar to that in Figure 10. Likewise, as the PAR content in the island-in-a-sea fiber increases, the peak is higher, sharper and narrower. Obviously, crystalline peak is clear with the PAR content because the PAR has high degree of crystallization originally. Using XRD curves, degree of crystallization as conditions such as spinning speed and the PAR content in the fiber is presented in Table 3. The values of degree of crystallization of the fiber have a same tendency of the XRD curves.

Figure 10. XRD curves of the PAR, PET and PAR/PET island-in-a-sea fiber as spinning speed

Figure 11. XRD curves of the PAR, PET and PAR/PET island-in-a-sea fiber as the PAR content

Table 3. Degree of crystallization of the PAR/PET island-in-a-sea fiber as spinning speed and the PAR content

Spinning speed (PAR content : 50wt%)	Degree of crystallization (%)
200m/min	20.02
300m/min	20.39
400m/min	21.74

PAR content (Spinning speed : 400m/min)	Degree of crystallization (%)
30wt%	14.78
50wt%	21.74
70wt%	29.50

Morphology of the PAR/PET island-in-a-sea fiber

The view of cross section of the PAR/PET island-in-a-sea fiber is shown in Figure 12. The island phase, PAR fiber, is located in the PET phase in the fiber. Also, it can be found that the PAR nanofibril which has a diameter about 90nm. The PAR content increases, the PAR nanofibrils are seen more packed closely in the PET phase. This morphology is one of the evidence in mechanical properties and crystallization properties.

(a) 30wt%

(b) 50wt%

(c) 70wt%

Figure 12. SEM photographs of the PAR/PET island-in-a-sea fiber as the PAR content: (a) 30wt%, (b) 50wt%, (c) 70wt%

3.2 Optimal condition of the PAR/PET composite

Tensile strength of the PAR/PET composite as a processing temperature

Figure 13 shows the DSC curves of the PAR and PET. The melting peak of PET is appeared at 250°C, while that of the PAR is at 295°C. Therefore, the experiment of molding temperature was conducted in the range of 250 to 275°C for no damage of the PAR phase. Tensile strength of the PAR/PET composite which was manufactured with molding temperature was shown in the Figure 14. At 265°C of molding temperature, the highest tensile strength about 400MPa is obtained. Over than 265 °C of molding temperature, tensile strength of the composite decreased. The damage of the PAR fiber due to relatively high heat was one of the immediate causes of the decrease of the tensile strength. From this result, 265°C was selected as a proper molding temperature of the PAR/PET composite.

Figure 13. DSC curves of the PAR and the PET

Figure 14. Tensile strength of the PAR/PET composite as processing temperature

Tensile strength of the PAR/PET composite as a processing pressure

In Figure 15, tensile strength increases as the composite manufacturing pressure increases until 500psi at 265°C for 10min. The highest tensile strength is obtained at the 500psi of molding pressure and then, rapid decrease in tensile strength is shown at 1000psi. It is due to high pressure causes high flow of the PET resin and it can scatter the alignment of the PAR fiber. Consequently, molding pressure of the composite manufacturing was determined at 500psi.

Figure 15. Tensile strength of the PAR/PET composite as processing pressure

Tensile strength of the PAR/PET composite as a processing time

As processing time is a little effect on tensile strength of the composite compared with the other conditions such as processing temperature and pressure which is shown in Figure 16. When the pressure of 500psi applied at 265°C for 5min, tensile strength shows the highest value over 800MPa among other processing times. In case of the processing time for 10min, tensile strength decreases but difference is a little. So, proper molding time under the conditions was determined at 5min.

Based on these experiments and data of tensile strength, the optimal condition of the PAR/PET composite manufacturing process is 265°C of temperature, 500psi of pressure, and 5min of processing time for manufacturing the PAR/PET composite.

Figure 16. Tensile strength of the PAR/PET composite as processing time

3.3 Characteristics of the PAR/PET composite

Tensile properties of the PAR/PET composite

Tensile strength and modulus of the PAR/PET composite with a spinning speed are shown in Fig 17. Tensile strength of the composite increases with a spinning speed, but the difference is not big. Tensile modulus of the composite increases as well and especially, the modulus of the composite which manufactured with the fiber spun by 200m/min is similar with that of the 300m/min. The composite with the fiber spun by 400m/min has the highest modulus in the samples. Overall, as the spinning speed of the PAR/PET island-in-a-sea fiber increases, tensile properties of the PAR/PET composites have a tendency of increase.

In Figure 18, tensile properties of the PAR/PET composite using the fiber with different the PAR content were represented. The difference of tensile strength is very steep and the tensile modulus of the composite shows a big difference with the PAR content. As a result, tensile properties of the PAR/PET composite increase largely with the PAR content in the fiber.

Figure 17. Tensile properties of the PAR/PET composite using the island-in-a-sea fiber as spinning speed

Figure 18. Tensile properties of the PAR/PET composite using the island-in-a-sea fiber as the PAR content

Flexural properties of the PAR/PET composite

In Figure 19 and 20, flexural properties of the PAR/PET composite are shown as spinning speed and the PAR content in the fiber. As a spinning speed increases, flexural strength and modulus increase gradually and it has same tendency with the tensile properties of the PAR/PET composite which shown in Figure 17 and 18. Also, the PAR content in the fiber for manufacturing the composite is more contained, flexural properties of the composite increase rapidly as well. Consequently, the flexural properties of the PAR/PET composite are more influenced on the PAR content than spinning speed of the island-in-a-sea fiber.

Figure 19. Flexural properties of the PAR/PET composite using the island-in-a-sea fiber as spinning speed

Figure 20. Flexural properties of the PAR/PET composite using the island-in-a-sea fiber as the PAR content

Crystallization properties of the PAR/PET composite

The crystallization properties of the PAR/PET composite using the island-in-a-sea fiber spun by different conditions are shown in Figure 21 and 22. Figure 21 represents the crystallization peaks of the PAR/PET composite as a spinning speed of the fiber. The locations of the peaks are same with the PAR/PET island-in-a-sea fiber, but the heights of the peaks are higher than that of the fiber. Also, all the peaks of the curves are sharp and narrow and especially, the height of the curve is higher as spinning speed increases. It is considered that the crystal is formed relatively clearly as a spinning speed increases.

Figure 22 shows the changes of the crystallization properties of the PAR/PET composite with the fiber having different PAR content. As the PAR content in the fiber increases, the peak of the composite using this fiber is more high and sharp. In other words, crystallization is clear by the PAR content in the fiber used for manufacturing the composite. When the PAR/PET composite manufactured using the fiber included 30wt% of PAR content, the crystallization properties are the best in the all of the conditions. Degree of crystallization of the PAR/PET composite using the fiber with conditions of spinning speed and the PAR content of the fiber is supposed in Table 4 and these results support the results of the XRD curves.

Figure 21. XRD curves of the PAR/PET composite using the island-in-a-sea fiber as spinning speed

Figure 22. XRD curves of the PAR/PET composite using the island-in-a-sea fiber as the PAR content

Table 4. Degree of crystallization of the PAR/PET composite using the island-in-a-sea fiber with different spinning speed and PAR content

Spinning speed (PAR content: 50wt%)	Degree of crystallization (%)
200m/min	25.06
300m/min	25.29
400m/min	27.06

PAR content (Spinning speed : 400m/min)	Degree of crystallization (%)
30wt%	23.02
50wt%	27.06
70wt%	33.31

Morphology of the PAR/PET composite

The fracture surface of the PAR/PET composite after tensile test is shown in Figure 23. In This observation, a sample having 50wt% of the PAR content was used. With the island phase of PAR, the PET sea phase is melted during the composite manufacturing process and constructed the matrix in the composite as shown. Figure 23 (a) suggests a typical morphology of cross sectional fracture of the PAR/PET composite with observation of relatively low magnification. Obviously, the PAR fiber bundle due to PAR fibrillation phenomena was shown as mentioned previously. However, fibrillation is scarcely occurred at the (b) which manufactured with 200m/min of spinning speed of the precursor fiber. In this case, tensile strength of the fiber was lower compared than the other samples, and thus, it is considered that the reinforcement has relatively low drawing effect and the fiber was fractured easily without fibrillation. While the photographs of the (b) and (c) showed that the PAR nanofibrils were fully packed in the PET matrix. Especially, the composite using the fiber with 400m/min of spinning speed of the fiber has many fibrils in the matrix.

Totally, the reinforcements of the composites with all of the conditions are distributed uniformly in the matrix of the composites.

(a) typical morphology of the composite using the island-in-a-sea fiber (400m/min)

(b) 200m/min

(c) 300m/min

(d) 400m/min

Figure 23. SEM photographs of the PAR/PET composite using the island-in-a-sea fiber as a spinning speed of the island-in-a-sea fiber (PAR content=50wt%) : (a) typical morphology of the composite (low magnification), (b) 200m/min, (c) 300m/min, (d) 400m/min

4 Conclusions

In this study, the PAR/PET island-in-a-sea fibers having different spinning conditions such as the spinning speed and the PAR content were used to manufacture the PAR/PET composite. Various molding parameters were investigated to establish the optimum manufacturing condition of the PAR/PET composites with tests and evaluations of the molded composites. From the study, some conclusions were obtained as following.

Mechanical properties of the PAR/PET island-in-a-sea fiber increase as spinning speed and the PAR content in the fiber increase. Also, mechanical properties of the fiber are more affected by the PAR content than the spinning speed. As a spinning speed of the PAR/PET island-in-a-sea fiber is fast, degree of crystallization becomes high because it has a similar effect of drawing process of the PAR phase. The optimal molding condition of the PAR/PET composite is obtained at 265°C of temperature, 500psi of pressure, and 5min of processing time.

The PAR/PET composites with the fiber having different conditions showed a big difference in the flexural properties. However, tensile properties of the composite showed relatively small difference as spinning speed and the PAR content in the fiber. The degree of crystallization of the PAR/PET composite is higher than that of the PAR/PET island-in-a-sea

fiber. Because the PAR fiber and its nanofibrils are orientated in the fiber direction very well and distributed uniformly in the composite, so they contributed the improvement of mechanical properties and flexural properties of the PAR/PET composite.

Totally, the mechanical properties and degree of crystallization of the PAR/PET island-in-a-sea fiber and its composite have a same tendency, and they were improved with spinning speed and the PAR content.

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References

- [1] Materials&Design, D. Romanzini, A. Lavoratti, H. L. Ornaghi, S. C. Amico, A. J. Zattera, Vol. 47, pp 9-15, 2013.
- [2] J. Appl. Polym. Sci., S. S. Huo, V. S. Chevail, C. A. Ulven, Vol. 128, No. 5, pp 3490-3500, 2013.
- [3] Composite part B-engineering, M. Ramesh, K. Palanikumar, K. H. Reddy, Vol. 48, pp 1-9, 2013.
- [4] Journal of membrane science, S. D. Wanjale, U. K. Kharul, J. P. Jog, Vol. 306, No.1-2, pp 277-286, 2007.
- [5] J. Balk Tribol Assoc., G.V. Kozlov, A. I. Burya and G. E. Zaikov, Vol.13, No.1, pp 24-28, 2007.
- [6] Colloids and surfaces A-Physicochemical and engineering aspects, C. A. Fuentes, L. Q. N. Tran, M. Van Hellemont, V. Janssens, C. Dupont-Gillain, A. W. Van Vuure, I. Verpoest, Vol. 418, pp 7-15, 2013.
- [7] J. Appl. Polym. Sci., S. Yesil, G. Bayram, Vol. 127, No. 2, pp 982-991, 2013.
- [8] J. Appl. Polym. Sci., X. S. Zeng, D. M. Cai, Z. D. Lin, X. Cai, X. J. Zhang, S. Z. Tan, Y. B. Xu, Vol. 126, No. 2, pp 601-607, 2012.
- [9] J. Polym. Mater., M. E. A. Mohsin, I. Ali, R. H. Elleithy, S. M. Al-Zahrani, Vol. 29, No. 1, pp 89-100, 2012.
- [10] J. Thermoplast. Compos. Mater., T. Huq, A. Khan, T. Akter, N. Noor, K. Dey, B. Sarker, M.

- Saha, R. A. Khan, Vol. 24, No. 6, pp 889-898, 2011.
- [11] Express polymer letters, J. C. Chen, C. M. Wu, F. C. Pu, C. H. Chiu, Vol. 5, No. 3, pp 228-237, 2011.
- [12] Polymer, H. B. Zhang, W. G. Zheng, Q. Yan, Y. Yang, J. W. Wang, Z. H. Lu, G. Y. Ji, Z. Z. Yu, Vol. 51, No. 5, pp 1191-1196, 2010.
- [13] Sen-I-Gakkaishi, K. Watanabe, H. Iijima, Vol. 54, No. 4, pp 124-128, 1998.
- [14] Compos. Sci. Technol., J. A. Mapkar, A. Belashi, L. M. Berhan, M. R. Coleman, Vol. 75, pp 1-6, 2013.
- [15] Cement&Concrete composites, Z. S. Metaxa, M. S. Konsta-Gdoutos, S. P. Shah, Vol. 36, No. SI, pp 25-32, 2013.
- [16] Composite part B-engineering, Q. Chen, Y. Zhao, Z. P. Zhou, A. Rahman, X. F. Wu, W. D. Wu, T. Xu, H. Fong, Vol. 44, No. 1, pp 1-7, 2013.
- [17] J. Polym. Environ., M. Jonoobi, A. P. Mathew, M. M. Abdi, M. D. Makinejad, K. Oksman, Vol. 20, No. 4, pp 991-997, 2012.
- [18] ACS Applied materials&Interfaces, T. Wang, L. T. Drzal, Vol. 4, No. 10, pp 5079-5085, 2012.
- [19] J. Appl. Polym. Sci., C. Y. Chang, E. M. Philips, R. Liang, S. W. Tozer, B. Wang, C. Zhang, H. T. Chiu, Vol. 128, No.3, pp 1360-1368, 2013.
- [20] Kobunshi ronbunshu, T. Yamazaki, T. Nishino, K. Otsuka, Y. Takenaka, H. Nakashima, Y. Mawatari, M. Tabata, Vol. 69, No.6, pp 274-282, 2012.
- [21] Industrial&Engineering chemistry research, S.C. Roh, K.W. Song, C. K. Kim, Vol. 50, No. 22, pp 12596-12605, 2011.
- [22] Chem. Mater. B. F. Zhang, Z. G. Wang, Vol. 22, No. 9, pp2780-2789, 2010.
- [23] Separation science and technology, Y. J. Chendake, Y. S. Bhole, H. R. Lohokare, U. K. Kharul, Vol. 45, No. 2, pp 163-171, 2010.